

YOUTHS AND COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT: OVERCOMING THE 21ST CENTURY CHALLENGES

Moses Idongesit Peters¹
Nsidibe Akpan Usoro²
Godwin Nse Ekong²
Aniebiet Christian James¹

¹Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus
perfectakwastar@gmail.com, mosesidongesit@aksu.edu.ng,
Phone: 09055479040

²University of Uyo, Uyo

Abstract

Youths are considered as the strength of every nation, state and community. Youths are considered as the future of every society and their involvement in the development of their society from the grassroots is an inevitable tool of development especially in the 21st century. This paper examined the roles and the challenges of youth participation in community development as are experienced and perceived in this period. Community Development Theory and Practices was engaged as a theoretical guide for the study. Secondary data were analysed for Community Development Approaches, roles of youth in community development, challenges of youth participation in community development in the 21st century, and how to overcome challenges of youth participation in community development in the 21st century. The paper concluded that the world is witnessing the largest number of youth as compare to the early centuries of the world. This population of the youth is presenting human resources for community transformation through engagement in community development projects. Youths are valuable resources for organizations and groups involvement in community development.

Keywords: youths, development, challenges, community development, and 21st century

INTRODUCTION

Youth are the driving strength of every society and it is their innovativeness, character and will power that defines course of developmental (Kabonga, 2016). Africa has the youngest, largest and fastest growing population in the world (AU, 2000). According to African Union (2000), there is a public perception of youth as opportunities and threats due to the energetic nature of the age cohort. According to National Youth Policy of Nigeria (2019), a youth in Nigeria includes citizens of the Federal Republic of Nigeria aged 18 – 29 years. Youths characterized the largest portion of the Nigerian population both at urban centres and rural areas (Peters, Bassey, Usoro and Samuel, 2022). According to United Nation (1981), youth are human citizens of member nations between 15 – 24 years without prejudice to other definitions by Member States. Sociologically, a youth is a period in

which adult identities are shaped and through this society's institutions and cultural beliefs are either reproduced or remade. Raymond & Isigwe (2019) defined youth as whoever is young, fresh and vibrant both in looks and at heart, full of hope, of promise, enthusiastic ideas even at 70 years.

Before we could establish the nexus between youth and development, it is worthwhile to look at the concept of development. The purpose of development according to SID (2021) is a rise in the level and quality of life of the population, and the creation or expansion of local regional income and employment opportunities, without damaging the resources of the environment. Development is visible and useful, not necessarily immediately, and includes an aspect of quality change and the creation of conditions for a continuation of that change (SID, 2021).

According to Ajala (2021), development must be people driven if it has to be effective and achievable. Development has to be community based and community driven because development has to affect human beings. Development can be effective and productive when it is community based. United Nations defines community development as a process where community members come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems (UN, n. d.). Development is a broad concept, applied to the practices of civic leaders, activists, involved citizens, and professionals to improve various aspects of communities, typically aiming to build stronger and more resilient local communities (UNTERM, 2014). Moreland and Lovett (1997) see community development as a learning process that involves people in experiences from which they will learn ways of enhancing their capacity for self-directed activity and destiny.

According to Hamilton (1992), community development process engages in politics, leadership, power attainment, group dynamics, learning, and social change. Community development is a holistic approach grounded in principles of empowerment, human rights, inclusion, social justice, self-determination and collective action (Kenny, 2007). According to Kenny (2007), community development is fundamentally based on the values of human rights, social justice, equality and respect for diversity. The principles which underpin the practice of community development is self-determination which implies that the people and communities have the right to make their own choices and decisions about their progress (Kenny, 2007). According to Phillips and Pittman (2009), community development is a method employed to facilitate community members to come together and discuss solutions to deal with current and common challenges in their societies which according to Khin (2017) implies that community development is a way to motivate community members to get involved in action-taking in order to achieve desirable or shared results for their members.

The 21st Century has presented the youth in the developing communities in the third world countries like Nigeria with a call for development from their roots. The youth who are the energetic force of community development are faced with either developing their roots (communities) or forced to migrate to where they expect urbanism and contributes to such on daily basis. This implies that youth' participation is a key factor to community development. Youth' involvement in community development programme has been as long as man's existence and their contribution towards community development has much to be desired. Youths can be motivated by mature adults to be

involved in community development. Peters et al., (2022) posits that parents are considered to be adults who have undergone cultural socialization and this has positioned parents at an influential point over their children. It is generally accepted in most developing countries like Nigeria, that government alone cannot develop all the rural communities as at when due and the youths have great role in this project (Sprojeetng, 2021). Youth participation in community development especially in the rural areas of Nigeria has witness many challenges in recent times. This may be because of the confused status accredited to the youth which in some cases the youth are considered as threats by virtue of the risk factors associated with the violent actions of some or groups of youth which make them to be problematic due to their involvement in politics, socio-cultural groups and deviant. Such attitudes presume that young people are easily lured into participating in violent actions in the context where widespread unemployment and socioeconomic vulnerabilities are on the rise (Kenny, 2007). In the other way, the youth are considered to be solution due to their population, energetic nature of their age cohort, mental capacities, will-power, and availability. Such attitudes presume that young population are at the forefronts of positive innovation and social change that contribute to economic growth and development (Kenny, 2007). It is expedient for us to examine the roles and the challenges of youth participation in community development as are experienced and perceived in this period and geographical location which is what is paper sought to achieve.

Community Development Theory and Practices

O'Connor and Brady (2014) cited in Khin (2017) proposed a theoretical model, which enables community members to get involved with community organising, including community building, trust building for future plans, and mobilising individuals. Deducing from O'Connor and Brady conceptual framework, it can be said that to achieve the mentioned concepts (community building, trust building for future plans), motivation and empowerment play a vital role in mobilization of youth for community development and propelling the people to own their development goals and processes. According to Khin (2017), community has its own attachment in terms of potential and weaknesses where it might need to be stagnant or developed based on the community members' decisions, choices, managements and solutions. O'Connor and Brady model seeks to propel youth into community development through community building, trust building for future plans, driven by motivation. This theoretically implies that through motivation youth are likely to engage in community building and trust building for future plans which are the composition of community development.

Community Development Approaches

According to legit (2021), there are various approaches to the idea of community development. While some of them focus on the processes taking place in the communities, others focus on the outcomes/objectives. These approaches include:

- **Community Engagement:** This approach is focused on facilitating understanding, exchange of information to build social capital and enhance social outcomes through a decision-making process.

- **Women Self-help Group:** It is focused on the contribution of women in the communities' development.
- **Community Capacity Building:** It is concerned with helping communities in obtaining, strengthening, and maintaining the ability to set and achieve their own development goals.
- **Large Group Capacitation:** This approach is related to an adult education and social psychology development. It is aimed at the increase of activity of the large groups of unemployed or semi-employed citizens, often with Lower Levels of Literacy (LLL).
- **Social capital formation:** An approach focused on the cooperation between individuals and large social groups.
- **Nonviolent direct action:** This kind of action is aimed at revealing an existing problem, highlighting an alternative, and demonstrating a possible solution to an existing social problem. Economic development is focused on the development of developing countries to increase the level of economic, political, and social welfare of the community members. Sustainable development is aimed at achieving, in a balanced way, economic community development and environmental protection outcomes.
- **Community-driven development (CDD):** an economic community development approach that moves an emphasis from the activity of the central government to local communities.
- **Asset-based community development (ABCD):** is a method that seeks to use the strengths of the community as a means for its stable development.
- **Faith-based community development:** is known to utilize faith-based communities to cause community development increase.
- **Community-based participatory research (CBPR):** is an approach to the research that brings together the efforts of the community members and researchers in the research of the community life and problems. All the partners are expected to contribute the expertise, integrate and share their knowledge to make the process of decision making easier and more effective.
- **Community organizing:** is an approach assuming that social change involves conflicts and social struggles that can be a way to generate collective power for the powerless people.
- **Participatory planning:** includes community-based planning. This approach implies that the community is involved in the strategic and management processes of social planning on various levels of urban or rural social life.
- **Language-based development or Language revitalization:** This approach is focused on the use of a language as a means of serving the community. This involves the creation of books, films, and other media in the language development which is expected to help a community to develop its culture.

Roles of Youth in Community Development

According to Checkoway and Gutierrez (2006) cited in Khin (2017), youth have been viewed

as potential community assets for the last couple of decades, and are no longer viewed as a social problem. Khin further maintained that this is because young people are able to utilise their skills and make use of their rights to engage themselves in the development of their society. The roles of youths in community development include;

- Security
- Leadership
- Social capital mobilization
- Participation
- **Security:** According to United Nation (2017), unemployment and economic insecurity increase youth's vulnerability to political manipulation, criminal activity or joining violent extremist groups. Youth struggle to secure decent and dignified livelihoods, describing a system of limited options and support, in which finding drugs and small arms is often easier than finding jobs (UN, 2017). Security is an important factor in community development. This is so because without security development cannot be achieved and sustained. Many projects have been vandalized and some destroyed in different communities because of absent of security or dependent only on the Nigerian Police for security. One of the greatest challenges facing community development in Nigeria is insecurity. Insecurity has become a visible characteristic of most of the communities in Nigeria. Youth have been the core instrument of insecurity vices and engaging the youth in security matters of their community is an approach of development in the right direction. Youth today have formed part of the security projects of some communities in Nigeria. Youth form community vigilante groups for community security which is the bedrock for sustainable community development.
- **Leadership:** According to UNICEF (2020), the positioning of youth in society has a bearing on their leadership potential and their possible role in peace building. The tension between young and old has been one of the key features of inter-generational shifts pertaining to the control over power, resources and people toward community development projects (UNICEF, 2020). The tension experienced lies in the overt impatience of youth, their desire to strive for more, their willingness to be seen as responsible and capable, and the structural barriers to their social mobility (UNICEF, 2020). Youth have capacity to attain socially described adult status which qualifies them for leadership responsibility. Mobilization of youths for community development participation requires the inclusion of youths in decision making processes which will propel youth's motivation for participation.
- **Social capital mobilization:** Social capital is a great asset of any community as factor that enhances community development. Mobilization of social capital enhances smooth and sustainable community development. Base on the population of youth in various communities, building social capital is expedient for human capacity mobilization towards community development. Social capital can be mobilizes through forming various types of associations among the youth age cohorts. These associations can be positioned for

community development projects intervention, participations and contributions. Youths groups are mediums for social capital mobilization. Youth groups create platform through which young people meet for partnership, social relations, cooperation, future planning, resources harmonization, participation, and execution of interest. This ensures that youth have capacity to mobilize themselves by means of social capital toward effective participation in community development.

- **Participation:** this refers to different mechanisms through which the youths express opinions and ideally exert influence regarding political, economic, management, cultural or other social decisions and actions. Opportunity to express opinion and exert influence is the catalyst through the youth is motivated toward community development. Despite the population of the youth age cohort, it is their given opportunities to express their opinions and exert certain level of influence in decision making, action taking, and resources mobilizations that enhance the possibilities of community development participation among youth. Participation in community development is certain through creating opportunities for youth to express their organized and coordinated opinions and exerting certain level of influence in the community and community projects/programmes.

Challenges of Youth Participation in Community Development in the 21st century

The benefits of youth participation are substantial, however implementing, continuing and developing youth participation strategies in health, mental health and/or community programs can be diminished, inhibited or interrupted by a range of challenges (ngopulse, 2021). Knowing what these are can assist in reducing their impact and one of the first steps in developing youth participation strategies is to identify the barriers that may affect young people's ability to participate in developing their communities. These challenges are listed as:

- A lack of trust of young people in decision-making systems
- Poor information about how to become involved in youth participation
- Insufficient time due to education and/or work obligations and family/friend commitments
- Location and lack of good transportation system
- Skills deficits, for example in literacy, verbal skills and public speaking
- Low socio-economic status, for example unemployment and homeless young people
- Lack of confidence, by both young people
- Insufficient resources
- Minimal power given to young people to initiate organisational change
- Negative social attitudes to, and gender stereotyping of young people
- Lack of clarity about roles and responsibilities
- Inequality, with class distinctions preventing young people from lower income backgrounds

to interact with, and assume responsibilities in conjunction with, those from high-income background.

How to Overcome Challenges of Youth Participation in Community Development in the 21st Century

According to Barnett and Kumaran (2012), community participation helps youth become empathetic citizens who could potentially continue similar work when they become adults and youth who give back to their communities develop leadership skills, learn the importance of helping, and gain work experience. This is suffice for effective community development through engaging appropriate measures in overcoming challenges of youth participation in community development in the 21st century. The following measures can be taken to overcome the challenges of youth participation in community development in the 21st century;

- Give youth an opportunity to contribute and offer their input.
- Allow active collaboration between adults and youth; integrate youth into committees with adults who can act as mentors.
- Form relationships with elders who engage youth in community concerns to increase youth involvement.
- Connect youth to policy efforts by including them in the assessment of current policies and potential policies.
- Encourage youth to identify their own interests and activities where they can make positive changes.
- Allow youth to confront serious social problems and become active community citizens.
- Evaluate youth involvement efforts on a regular basis to identify and capitalize on strengths, identify and address weaknesses, and help gain more meaningful youth participation.
- Create interactive content with a purpose that encourages youth to take part

Conclusion

The world is witnessing the largest number of youth as compare to the early centuries of the world. This population of the youth is presenting human resources for community transformation through engagement in community development projects. Youths are valuable resources for organizations and groups involvement in community development. By encouraging and allowing opportunities for adult-youth-collaboration, community organizations can help youth learn valuable skills and prepare them to become civically engaged adults with functioning minds of development. Though in most cases youth are considered as problematic due to their energetic age cohorts and vulnerability to manipulations by elders into political and other activities, youth are great instruments for community development when given opportunity to express their opinion and exert certain amount of influence in issue concerning their communities. The 21st century is presenting the youth with diverse challenges, but giving the youth opportunities to contribute and offer input is the first step of overcoming the challenges facing the 21st century youth participation in community development.

REFERENCES

- African Union (2000). A Study on the Roles and Contributions of Youth to Peace and Security in Africa. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. 14p
- Ajala, A. S. (2021). Anthropology and Development in Africa – From Theory To Practice. A Lecture Presented at the Valedictory Ceremony of Professor I.V.Modo, Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Uyo, Uyo, Nigeria.
- Barnett, R. V & Kumaran, M. (2012). “[Involving Youth in the Community Development Process \(FCS9253\)](#),” UF/IFAS Department of Family, Youth and Community Sciences.
- Hamilton, E. (1992). *Adult Education for Community Development*. New York: Greenwood Press.
<http://www.ngopulse.org/article/2021/07/23/youth-participation-community-development>
- Kabonga, I. (2016). Youth and Development in Ward Three of Chegutu District, Zimbabwe. *IJRSS* 6(2): 1p
- Kenny, A. (2007). Community Development. retrieved online on 20th December, 2021 from <https://gamingsection.net/news>
- Khin, S. A. (2017). Youth Participation in Community Development. Unpublished Thesis Submitted to the Victoria University of Wellington. Retrieved as pdf file on 21st December, 2021
- Legit (2021). Community Development. Retrieved from <https://www.legit.ng/1208558-what-community-development.html>
- Moreland, R., & Lovett, T. (1997). Lifelong learning and community development. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 16(3), 201-216.
- Peters, M. I., Basse, A. E., Usoro, N. A. and Samuel, M. E. (2022). Hymn No 4: A Novel Psychoactive Substance Consumption among Ibibio Youths of The Niger Delta Region. *International Journal of Education and Science Development (IJESD)* 1(2): 20 – 33p
- Phillips, R., & Pittman, R. H. (2009). An Introduction to Community Development. New York: Routledge.
- Raymond, N. & Isigwe, P. O. (2019). The Nigerian Youth and National Development: A Prescriptive Exploration. *Journal of Public Administration and Social Welfare Research* 4 (1): 1-6p
- Society for International Development SID (2021). What is Development? Retrieved from <https://sid-israel.org/en/what-is-development/> on 19th December, 2021
- Sprojectng (2021). The Role of Youth In Community Development. retrieved online from <https://sprojectng.com/the-role-of-youth-in-community-development> on 20th December, 2021
- UNICEF (2020). The Role of Youth in Peace Building: Challenges and Prospects/ retrieved from <https://gdc.unicef.org/resource/role-youth-peacebuilding-challenges-and-opportunities>
- United Nation (2017). Youth and Security. Retrieved on 20th December, 2021
- United Nation (n. d.). Community Development. Retrieved online on 20th December, 2021
- UNTERM (2014). "[Community development](#)". Retrieved online on 20th December, 2021